

TEACHING ENGLISH PHONETICS LANGUAGE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Teaching correct pronunciation is an important activity of a teacher in English. Formation of phonetic skills among students of Uzbek non-linguistic colleges and schools has its own characteristics: the presence in most colleges and universities in the English language teaching program is not an introductory-correctional, but an accompanying phonetics course, inclusion in it is not only gaming, but also traditional phonetic exercises, widespread use information and communication technologies.*

Keywords: *activity of a teacher, phonetic skills, phonetic sounds, teaching program, phonetic exercises.*

Work practice in kindergarten and schools, conversations with secondary vocational teachers and higher educational institutions testify that college graduates, when entering a university, need special pedagogical support in the formation of auditory pronunciation skills. Many of them have a break in learning English, there are various factors leading to a decrease in motivation; this category of students lacks the skills to work independently on phonetics. The article suggests solutions problems faced by college graduates, when developing phonetic skills at school. Leading methodologists in the field of teaching foreign languages and practicing teachers unanimously consider it an important area of pedagogical activity for a foreign language teacher at all levels of education, the formation of phonetic skills in students - the ability to correctly perceive sound sample, associate it with meaning and adequately reproduce. For college and university students of all specialties and areas of training, developed phonetic skills as part of intercultural competence allow for competent intercultural communication. Future specialists with secondary vocational education, whose professional activities related to a foreign language, for example, tourism specialists and hospitality, as well as for employees of those organizations and enterprises, among whose employees or clients there may be foreign citizens, correct pronunciation and understanding of spoken speech allows you to phonetically correctly carry out professional activity. For specialists with higher education, phonetic skills become even more important. If they are not sufficiently formed, understanding the speech of a foreign language becomes difficult, business partner, and also the social assessment of their own speech in the eyes of the interlocutor decreases. The purpose of this work is to identify features, common and different in the current state of teaching phonetics to Russian students non-linguistic colleges and universities, identify problems in the field of phonetics that exist during the transition from one level of professional education to another, and suggest ways to solve them. Primary and secondary school students need not a theory, but a large number of carefully selected and well structured phonetic exercises, and at the next stages of training, theoretical information is also needed. Patricia Ashby recommends starting each stage of learning English from the introductory and correctional phonetic course. Now let's look at how work is being done to develop phonetic skills in Uzbek schools and kindergarten. First-year children linguistic education continuing to study

English as the first foreign language, are generally familiar with the pronunciation English sounds, stress, word patterns and intonation designs from the basic and secondary general education course schools. In recent years, we have noted an increase in the quality of knowledge on foreign language in general and the ability to correctly pronounce the most common words of the English language and understand learning common phrases in particular. However first-year children and pupils admit both phonetic (not interfering with communication, for example softening of consonants), and phonological errors (changing meaning of the word and thereby preventing communication, for example, deafening consonants at the end of the word, changing duration of vowel sounds).

In Uzbek kindergarten and schools the question of including an introductory and remedial course in phonetics in the training program for students continuing to study English as a first foreign language is decided by a teacher working in a particular student group. In his decision he usually relies on data obtained during entrance testing, and most often phonetics in non-linguistic colleges and universities is not highlighted as a separate aspect of training. To overcome phonetic difficulties encountered by pupils, there is usually an accompanying phonetics course—phonetic exercises included by the teacher in the classroom lesson plan. The goal of this course is to improve and automate auditory pronunciation skills. Phonetic material in the accompanying phonetics course studied in the following volume:

1. Consonants and vowels in different phonetic positions, combinations consonants, vowel combinations, pronunciation of grammatical forms words;
2. Rhythmic patterns of polysyllabic words, groups of words with constant and moving stress;
3. Unity of pronunciation of words in speech: unstressed words and words with weakened stress;

English teachers have many interesting methodological ideas for working on phonetics. The leadership of British Methodists in this area is undeniable. For example, Nary Tomes suggests using interesting exercises for teaching phonics, such as games with cards, rubber bands, homemade board games, phonetic dominoes, clapping games clapping, games in motion, intonation ladders, games with kazoo (pipe, toy wind musical instrument), lollipop, dubbing cartoons and others. . These and others like them exercises being introduced into the practice of Russian education at all levels. The accompanying phonetics course uses and exercises such as reciting proverbs, sayings, rhymes, listening to short stories on the topic of the lesson, listening to songs. In uzbek colleges and universities, when teaching pronunciation, in addition to games, traditional exercises are also used. At the stage of introducing new vocabulary, this is the repetition of words and phrases teacher and independently, listening to audio applications to textbooks, work with Internet resources. Foundation and central an element of an English language lesson in non-linguistic colleges and universities in uzbek is the text, and work on phonetics continues in the course of performing pre-text assignments and exercises, reading the text and completing post-text tasks. For students who have difficulties in the field of phonetics, we remind them of the rules for reading letters and letter combinations. A big plus is that the model of English pronunciation for college and university students is currently it is not only the teacher's speech that serves. There are many resources on the Internet dedicated to the phonetics of the English language. Phonetics materials for English language learners are available at British Council website <http://premierskillenglish.britishcouncil.org>, British publishing houses Cambridge University Press, Oxford University Press, Pearson, Macmillan. The website <https://www.engvid.com>

presents many video lessons from experienced native teachers English language, including lessons aimed at staging pronunciation.

From this selection, we can recommend the website <http://www.native-english.ru/pronounce/organs> to students of non-linguistic colleges and universities. Materials this site helps in training the articulation of sounds and is very useful for understanding the peculiarities of English pronunciation, stress and intonation. From multimedia programs designed for teaching phonetic means of communication, is widely known. This program gives students the opportunity interactively compare your pronunciation with the standard one.

English language teachers at Russian universities have also accumulated experience in creating multimedia aids for teaching phonetics on their own, for example, such an aid is described in the work. Many institutions of secondary vocational and higher education from time to time invite foreign specialists and native-speaking teachers to give lectures and conduct master classes, and students have the opportunity to listen to their speech, paying attention not only to the content, but also to the pronunciation.

Internet resources on phonetics, multimedia manuals and educational computer programs, live communication with native speakers - all this contributes to more successful development of students.

Uzbek schools and kindergarten phonetic skills and abilities than, for example, a decade ago. Despite the fact that Russian colleges and universities use similar methods and approaches to teaching phonics who entered the university.

College graduates experience certain difficulties in learning English, including pronunciation. Firstly, these difficulties are associated with the general psychological stress experienced by a young man - a college graduate who initially prepared himself for the activity of a performer and graduated from college and then entered a university, having made the decision move to another level of education in order to expand their career prospects, often after a gap of several years.

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